

Entrepreneurship Learning Based on Literacy Skill Conservation

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ABSTRACT

Basic literacy comprising reading, writing, and arithmetic skills that have been possessed by one illiterate must be maintained and improved so that relapsing does not take place. In other sides, the learning of literacy for adults' learners must be meaningful, giving economical and living values enabling the learners to improve their living standards through entrepreneurship education oriented to culture and local potential. These two combinations are the bases for the choice of education model in this study and is called entrepreneurship education based on literacy program. By combining these two aspects in its implementation, the learners are expected to be able to maintain and improve their possessed literacy and their entrepreneurship ability based on culture and local potential. This study employed descriptive analytical method. Involving 100 learners from three groups of Community Learning Centers in Pantura area, including Community Learning Center of Family Indramayu Regency, Community Learning Center of Bina Kreatif Bahari of Cirebon Regency, and Community Learning Center of Bima Sakti of Subang Regency as the source of data, this study revealed that entrepreneurship education based on literacy program could improve the ability of learners in reading, writing, and arithmetic.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurship, literacy conservation, local potential*

A. INTRODUCTION

Adult literacy skill maintenance program is one effort to continuously maintain reading and writing skills, preventing them from relapsing and realizing the target of improving literacy level of society. UNESCO (1993, 86-87) highlights three important factors contributing to the success of post literacy program and activities, namely: 1) program existence with systematic-based basic literacy program; 2) reading habit development in public; and 3) systematic and comprehensive action plan availability.

Post literacy in general is an activity to improve literacy through entrepreneurship learning to independently

improve learners' productivity both individually and in group after participating in the program and/or achieving basic competence of literacy. Similar program has been conducted in Uganda, known as Functional Adult Literacy (FAL) that encourages learners' empowerment using the concept of conscientization. (Akello, Lutwama-Rukundo, & Musiimenta, 2017).

The importance of illiterate eradication program can be comprehensively and extensively read in the following website; www.paudni.kemdikbud.go.id, releasing several big challenges in the eradication program itself, including: 1) characteristics of illiterate society, the remains of 4.02%

are under poverty, isolated and spread, and some live within particular culture; 2) the increasing number of new illiterates due to relapsing; 3) the increasing number of illiterate potentials attributed to the number of drop out early elementary schoolers (grade 1-3).

Relapsing factor has always become the main source of problem in the adult illiterate eradication. To minimize the problem, continuous literacy learning program is required to empower society by applying whatever means defining effective methods. This literacy learning is crucial due to the fact that low literate level has become stigmatized within society, giving them difficulties to get empowered (Parikh, Parker, Nurss, Baker, & Williams, 1996). One comprehensive and integrated model of illiterate eradication program is through an entrepreneurship activity, expected to give direct impacts on the improvement of society's living standard. This entrepreneurship activity is integrated with literacy learning and is realized through a program of making chips from fishbone and making fish roasted shredded fish.

In general, this study is intended to achieve the following aims: (1) to improve the quality of Indonesian language of society living in isolated, left behind, and marginalized areas in Pantura areas in West Java Province, and (2) to develop life skills in order to build soft skill and hard skill beneficial for individual and community needs. Literacy is used as potential mediator. Literacy can be conceptualized as the mingle agent as to give impact on the achievement of higher education. There is a possibility to have a feedback circle with literate education, and reading-writing skills that possibly improve the target of higher education achievement (Thu T. Nguyen, Eric J. Tchetgen, Ichiro Kawachi, Stephen E. Gilman, Stefan Walter M. Maria Glymour, 2017). In particular, this study is conducted in order to analyze the implementation of Local Culture Basis Literacy Learning Model for adult learners'

illiterate eradication in listening, speaking, reading, writing, and arithmetic.

B. METHOD

The study employed descriptive analytical method. It was conducted in order to find out the impact of program implementation of literacy conservation based entrepreneurship education on the achievement of literacy learning covering skills of reading, writing, and arithmetic. The treatment given was in the form of education program for learners in Pantura areas, taking into account the empowerment of local culture, society empowerment in entrepreneur that is based on local potential, or in other words, education for sustainable development, the improvement of Indonesian language ability, and prevention from basic literacy relapsing.

The main source of data in this study involved; (1) 100 learners, coming from three community learning centers in Pantura areas, including 60 learners from Community Learning Center of Famili of Indramayu, 20 learners from Community Learning Center of Bima Kreatif Bahari, and 20 learners from Community Learning Center of Bima Sakti; (2) 3 management people of those community learning centers; (3) 10 tutors from these three Pantura areas in West Java. These main sources of data were learning groups under the foster program of Center for Development of Early Childhood Education of Community Education of West Java.

The data collected from the research were analyzed and categorized into five themes, as follows: 1) Syntax (Learning Structure), (2) Supporting system, (3) Social System, (4) Tutor's Role, and (5) The instructional and supporting impacts in order to form a comprehensive system of illiteracy eradication.

Learning model is developed by referring to the cultural social condition of learners who are mostly under poverty, who have participated in the basic literacy program yet indicated to experience relapsing, who are categorized as low

achievers in terms of Indonesian language mastery, and who lives in areas with rich culture of seashore society optimized for the source of learning. Therefore, it is important to align the learning materials with the natural environment familiar with the learners since familiarity brings or even enhances comprehension (Lipson, 1986).

C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Review on the Skills of Reading, Writing, and Arithmetic

The analysis of the data regarding learners' conservation of literacy on reading, writing, and arithmetic showed varying results. Some were high, others were middle, and the others were low. These results were considered normal since the target of the programs were adults. The distinctive result of literacy learning through entrepreneurship demonstrated positive results, showing that there were improvements in knowledge, attitude, and behavior. Literacy learning through entrepreneurship is one of functional literacy education programs. This is aligned with Kusnadi (2005: 53) stating that functional literacy is one of nonformal education programs (community education) for learners who have not yet mastered the skills of reading, writing, and arithmetic, and after participating in the program, they can apply the learning result in their lives. This literacy program is more successful if this is relevant with problems faced by learners, with their jobs, and supports their business development (Corus & Julie, 2011).

It indicates that they do not only possess reading, writing, and arithmetic skills, but also profession-related skills so that they can survive in their lives. EFA Global Report (2005: 150) defines literacy as a skill to read, write, and count. For illiterate adult learners, literacy skill is not only the ability to read, write, and count, but also the ability relevant with their daily needs. Literacy, in a broad sense, is defined along with the development of human's life such as visual literacy and knowledge in the

information field. Information literacy refers to the skill to access and use many sources of information to complete the knowledge. A study in Nigeria showed that the ability in reading accompanied with the ability in operating gadget such as Android supports the ability to look for information (Ukachi, 2015).

Further, the researcher thought that the conservation of literacy skills of learners who participated in the post basic literacy education or entrepreneurship literacy is the basic investment for literacy education learners in stimulating and empowering individuals to achieve all knowledge, value, skill, and understanding. It also encourages the learners to continuously use the remains time to keep learning to become an experienced individual with the hope that they can develop into literacy society, using functional literacy skill as their basis to start.

It is also in line with Jarvis (2007) stating that literacy society is the source of development that can improve individual and society to a better direction and further can change their culture so that they can respond to the changing dimensions of social, politics, economy, and new ethics emerging in the midst of society's life.

A study in NALS explained that adult American income is higher in each level of literacy (Wagner & Richard, 1999). It shows that the change encourages each individual to have access and broad opportunities to have lifelong learning, gradually forming a learning and literacy society.

Likewise, Ducker (1994) illustrated some features of literacy society, as follows: a) to possess academic skill, b) to have critical thinking, c) to orient to problem solving, d) to have ability to learn leaving old thoughts, and learning new things, e) to have a skill of individual and social development (including self confidence, motivation, commitment to moral and ethical values, a broad understanding of society and the world.

The main target of literacy society in Indonesia is the available access to broad education, competition and education relevance, and accountable education management, in line with Gani (2008) stating that the targets of literacy society in Indonesia are as follows: a) to provide adequate and equitable access to education for all citizens, leading to the improvement of the number of learning participation in society in all levels of education, b) to improve quality, competitiveness, and relevance of education for all Indonesian people in national and international levels, and c) to improve accountable governance in education both in the level of administration and education.

2. Review on the Result of Analysis of Pre and Post Tests

With respect to the skills of reading, writing, and arithmetic, literacy learners

learning through entrepreneurship training showed different results between pre and post tests. Before the treatment was given, the average score was 56.83, however after the treatment was given, the average score was 62.23. It indicates the gap between the pre and post test is 5.41 or 7.21%, implying that there is an increase in the skills of reading, writing, and arithmetic of literacy learners after participating in the program, aside from the lowest difference, which is 2 point. Further, the highest difference of score is 9 point or 12%. The pretest showed that in the beginning, the skills of reading, writing, and arithmetic of literacy learners were still low, however after the treatment of entrepreneurship training was given, the score increased by 5.41 point or 7.21%. To maintain clarity, the change can be seen in the figure below.

Fig. 3.8 Result of Pre dan Post Tests of Literacy Conservation
 Source: Result of Research Analysis, 2019

The graph shows that there is an increase in the skills of reading, writing, and arithmetic, and can be seen from five aspects as follows; first, learning method was based on the practice of entrepreneurship making the students become skillfull as it was applied in their daily lives (functional); second, content or

material delivered attracted the attention of learners, which was more observable by using the approach of entrepreneurship practice; third, high motivation of the participant in participating in the entrepreneurship learning program; fourth, high confidence that the participants will be able to improve their skills in reading,

writing, and arithmetic in their daily lives; and fifth the attractive, dialogic, and participative ways in materials delivery.

It means that the implementation of literacy education program is considered as a need to improve the will of learning and to give the change to a better direction. This is in line with Coombs (1985) illustrating that literacy education is the basic need that can trigger the development of society in village areas in developing countries.

Hunter in Kusnadi (2005) states that there are three basic categories to define literacy, in which each category is based on different assumptions from the role of literacy in society's life. Those assumptions are as follows.

- a. Literacy as set basic skill, abilities or competencies;
- b. Literacy as the necessary foundation for higher quality of life; and
- c. Literacy as reflection of political and structural realities.

UNESCO defines literacy as one skill to read and write simple sentences needed or known in everyday life. Someone is equipped with functional literacy skill if the person is involved in activities in which literacy skill is the pre-requirement as effective functions, as the basis to improve reading, writing, and arithmetic skills. In its practice, functional literacy is an approach to enable learners to read, write, and arithmetic integrated with extra activities needed, thus in the end the learners are skillful not only in the 3R's but also in problem solving.

H.S. Bhola (1984, 21) clearly stated that: *Literacy can be defined in instrumental terms as the ability to read and write in the mother tongue or in national language this is required by cultural and political realities. Numeracy the ability to deal with number at a primary level is typically considered part of literacy*"

The statement above clearly states that literacy is instrumentally relevant with human civilization in the forms of reading-writing skills as the main language used by every nation in the world. Literacy skill is

also highly relevant with the development of culture, including the interaction of all factors supporting the literacy itself. Literacy helps to reform the culture aligned with the wants of people within a community.

D. CONCLUSION

The result of the study concludes that literacy conservation based entrepreneurship education program has evidently improved literacy skills of learners with respect to reading, writing, and arithmetic. Therefore, basic literacy skills that have been mastered by the learners can be maintained and even improved to prevent from relapsing. The making use of culture and local potential in choosing learning materials and learning process are supporting factors that contribute to the success of learners learning process. Andragogy approach and social approach are the most appropriate choice for adult learners.

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